

Documentation of a Custom Input Device

This is the documentation for a custom input device for the project *Audiovisual Feedback to Augmented Manual Activities During Space Walks* as shown in Fig. 1. In the project, it was used as an input device in a VR environment to enable hands-on operation.

Fig. 1: Custom input device for use e.g. in VR environments.

Overview

The input device consists of a case mounted at standing height with several operating elements on its surface. A labeled overview of the control elements is shown in Fig. 2. As operating elements available there are a push-button and three rotary encoders on top and a lever on the side of the case. The lever is a modified ball valve that can be moved in a range of 90 degrees. The rest of the controls are standard components, with the rotary encoders having a step size of 15 degrees.

All the control elements are connected to a microcontroller inside of the case that can communicate with a computer via USB cable. For the VR application, an HTC Vive tracker was attached to the case to match the pose of the real device with its VR twin.

Fig. 2: Overview over the control elements and hardware components of the input device.

Dimensions and Mechanical Workings

The case is a retired plastic toolbox that has been visually enhanced with some sheet metal applications. It has a size of 26cm x 25cm x 11cm. The 3 rotary knobs have a diameter of 48mm, the button has a diameter of 44mm. They are mounted on the lid of the case with a centre-to-centre distance of 10cm x 10cm.

In the current configuration, the button is in the top left corner. However, the four control elements are mounted on a square support plate (on the inside of the lid) in such a way that they can be rotated with little effort and the button can be moved to any of the four positions.

The ball valve on the right side of the case was equipped with a potentiometer to detect its angular position. It can be seen in Fig. 3 with the installed poti. In order to create a mechanical connection between the potentiometer and the moving parts of the valve, a locking device was manufactured that was inserted into the ball of the valve and locked in place. Fig. 4 shows a sectional drawing of the ball valve with the locking device and poti. The locking device is a cylinder that fits into the ball of the valve and can be clamped in place with a setscrew. The axis of the potentiometer is inserted through a bore on the underside of the valve and is connected to the locking device by another setscrew.

Fig. 3: Inside view of the input device showing the electromechanical elements of the device connected to the microcontroller. With detail views of the microcontroller and the modified ball valve.

Fig. 4: Sectional drawing of the modified ball valve showing the locking device that mechanically connects the ball valve with the potentiometer.

Wiring

All the electromechanical control elements mentioned are connected to an *Adafruit Metro M4 Express* microcontroller, which analyses the status of the elements and sends it to the host computer via USB. A wiring diagram for all components is shown in Fig. 5.

Alternatively, the pin layout for the microcontroller is listed in the following table:

Component	Pin
Encoder 1 CLK	D0
Encoder 1 DT	D1
Encoder 2 CLK	D2
Encoder 2 DT	D3
Pushbutton	D4
Encoder 3 CLK	D5
Encoder 3 DT	D6
Potentiometer Wiper	A0
Potentiometer VCC	3.3V
Encoders VCC	5V
Pushbutton LED	5V

Fig. 5: Wiring diagram for the microcontroller and control elements.

Programming

The microcontroller runs *MicroPython*, a *Python 3* version for microcontrollers. The status of the controller is sent to the host as a list with 6 integer values at regular intervals. Note that the 3 rotary encoders are equipped with buttons that are not currently used, but they have already been taken into account in the code for future use cases.

The values of the potentiometer can theoretically lie between 0 and 65536. However, due to the mechanical limitation by the ball valve, the values are between approx. 35000 and 58000, depending on the angular offset between valve and poti. The values are output raw to enable more flexible processing on the host computer:

Index	Control Element	Values
0	Lever	0 - 65536
1	Pushbutton	0 - 1
2	Encoder 1	±1 Increments
3	Encoder 1 Button	0
4	Encoder 2	±1 Increments
5	Encoder 2 Button	0
6	Encoder 3	±1 Increments
7	Encoder 3 Burron	0